

MULTI-AGENT SYSTEMS APPROACHES FOR DYNAMIC APPLICATION SECURITY TESTING

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Abstract. Software security is important for the business as well to cut costs on developed software issues responding process. That is why security testing is also considered an indispensable part that must be automated. Current approaches for security testing such as Static Application Security Testing and Dynamic Application Security Testing are widely used and have its own merits and demerits. The most significant demerits of Dynamic Testing are incompatibility with some application architectures and resource intensiveness for on-premises versions. To address the problem of efficient resource allocation and management an Auction-based bidding approach can be used. Despite the effectiveness of DAST implementation with such algorithms, it has its own disadvantages, such as complicated session management and limitation only for web-based applications.

Keywords: application security, dynamic application security testing, multi-agent systems

Introduction. Enterprises are trying to minimize the costs of change during their software maintenance. That is why “Shift-left” approach is developed, which discussed in detail in Chapter 1.1. Chapter 1.2 describes how the software is tested with security and which popular approaches exist. The next Chapter 2.1 aims to represent crucial disadvantages of Dynamic Application Security Testing mentioned with the help of official documentations of the famous tools. Then, in Chapter 2.2 an approach to use Auction Bidding Algorithm to manage resources for DAST is given.

“Shift-left” approach. Usually, software is developed within several steps. Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) consists of five consequent phases [1]:

1. Requirement gathering
2. System Design
3. Development
4. Testing
5. Deployment

Each phase contributes to the entire software product in a different way and deviates different security risks. Therefore, an additional layer of security usually is introduced for each phase [2].

Figure 1. Source: Checkmarx

That classic SDLC model with security enhancements becomes Secure SDLC model or SSDLC. This approach makes it possible to use security methodologies and practices starting from the phase where the desirable software has not been written yet and only exists as an idea or a set of requirements. Looking at the cost of change, as software is not released yet or even written yet, it is cheap to make modifications in its design or code. [1] As we are approaching the real product the cost of change significantly increases (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Source: Long Island University

This idea creates a methodology called “Shift-left” approach where the goal is to introduce security techniques and tool kits as early as it possible to decrease the cost of response on security violations found in software and deliver secure product to the end user [2].

Static and Dynamic Application Security Testing

SAST. Static Applications Security Testing or SAST is designed to find vulnerable code patterns in applications. It can be applied in the Development phase of SDLC like an additional tool or extension for developers to analyze their code during writing and publishing or a standalone software that will check entire codebase of a software periodically or during the code review phase [3].

The main problem of SAST is the number of false positives that they can produce. During scan SAST creates a logical tree. As wider the logical tree is created, the results more accurate. However, for better language understanding, the focus should be put on one specific language or framework. That cause of dilemma problem of wider language support and deeper language understanding [5].

DAST. Dynamic Application Security Testing or DAST produces analysis during the runtime of application by sending malicious payloads to all possible or assigned interactions components (input boxes, forms, endpoints). After sending them it is waiting for their response to analyze whether the attempt was successful. [2][3]

As is understandable from the working principles of DAST, already working software is required. It means that the application is shifted right in comparison with SAST. However, it still can be applicable in Development and Testing phases.

One of the main DAST integration can be the complex and dynamic structure of an application that will prevent complete setting of DAST solution, for example, dynamic cookie names. [5].

Comparison. The overall comparison can be depicted like this (Table 1):

Table 1. Features of SAST and DAST

Feature	SAST	DAST
Quick scans		+
Faster integration	+	
Less false positives		+
Close to developer	+	

Since DAST solutions have less false-positive rate and, mostly, they do not require integration from the development side, they are still widely popular among security teams [6].

Analysis of current DAST solutions. The essence of Dynamic Application Security Testing is fuzzing. In the case of web applications, DAST agents like OWASP Zed Application Proxy (ZAP), create a site map. After, they are traversing the site map with producing the scan actions. According to the official OWASP ZAP documentation, it does not support parallel scans feature [7].

Commercial solutions such as Fortify Web Inspect can be deployed in a Kubernetes cluster. It supports parallel processing of JavaScript files among agents [8]. It is possible to conclude that only one solution supports parallel scanning of a web application and only in Kubernetes environment.

Vendor Synopsys highlights some of these problems by offering cloud-based solutions to get rid of DAST software installation and maintenance processes, including computing power losses due to allocation of that to the DAST software. However, it is not always possible to use cloud-based software due to internal policies and needs of the end user or enterprise [9].

Application of multi-agent systems approaches. Using the multi-agent approach, it is possible to allocate tasks using Auction-based algorithms from Game Theory. That technique is used in the field of Cloud Computing as well [10]. The idea is to distribute the site map across all agents involved according to their resource capabilities.

Traversal algorithm. First, let's define traversal algorithm. Traversal will consist of scanning the page and finding

- 1) Links to another web page – they will be added to the tasks list. That is a recursive task.
- 2) Targets for scans (example: input fields). Tasks are processed in an iterative way.

Task Allocation Negotiation. Before the scan, one of the agents is selected to be Master who will solve the allocation of task problem. The Master can be also deployed on a separate machine. A Free agent is an agent which finished the current iteration. When an agent becomes a Free agent, it asks the Master agent for new tasks. The Master combines the tasks that it has with further recourse iterations that agent found and gives the portion equals Free agent's bid. The rest is stored in Master Agent's task list until another agent becomes Free and approaches new tasks negotiation.

Implementation. A performance utility value is number that is calculated as:

$$P = C_p + N_p + M_p \quad (4)$$

where:

- P – performance utility value.
- C_p – CPU Performance.
- N_p – network Performance.
- M_p – memory Performance.

These metrics for calculation are mainly used in computing tasks, such as processing web page loading and sending web requests. Weight for each metric is selected based on importance of a particular component according to the task or environment (example: availability of the app in local network). It is opted to the system requirements which scanning engine should be used. It can be a custom scanning engine like OWASP ZAP. The only requisite is the ability of the scan engine to handle given path range rather than completely scan of the web application. Moreover, the scanning engine should handle the session itself. Of course, the system requirements can be adjusted so that all instances are on the same outgoing IP address from a gateway to mimic behavior of one agent doing multiple requests.

A real implementation attempt was made and published in GitHub [11]. As resource management Python is used. Different threads are played a role of agents with equal bidding. The scan engine is based on Python and Selenium, where all input fields are fuzzed with simple SQL injection query. The implementation was tested on basic Express.JS app with EJS template engine.

Conclusion. Software security has always played an important role in the Software Development field. Different techniques and approaches are used to make software secure and reliable just at the time of development. That is caused by the need of business to save money after a software reached the end user. To achieve that goal two main methods are implemented, namely Static and Dynamic Application Testin. Despite the focus on code of SAST, DAST is actively used with the propagation of botheration that is causing for the testing side, such as incompatibility with some applications architectures or operation of on-premises versions. Nevertheless, the implementation of the Auction algorithms with bidding can solve the problem of DAST process scaling and resource allocation.

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ПОДХОДЫ МУЛЬТИАГЕНТНЫХ СИСТЕМ ДЛЯ ДИНАМИЧЕСКОГО ТЕСТИРОВАНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИЛОЖЕНИЙ

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Аннотация. Безопасность программного обеспечения также необходима для бизнеса, чтобы сократить затраты на процесс реагирования на проблемы с разработанным программным обеспечением. Именно поэтому тестирование безопасности также считается незаменимой частью, которая должна быть автоматизирована. Современные подходы к тестированию безопасности, такие как статическое и динамическое тестирование безопасности приложений, широко используются и имеют свои достоинства и недостатки. Наиболее существенными недостатками динамического тестирования являются несовместимость с некоторыми архитектурами приложений и ресурсоемкость локальных версий. Для решения проблемы эффективного распределения ресурсов и управления ими может быть использован подход аукционных торгов. Несмотря на эффективность реализации DAST с помощью таких алгоритмов, она имеет свои недостатки, такие как сложное управление сессиями и ограничение только для веб-приложений.

Ключевые слова: безопасность приложений, динамическое тестирование безопасности приложений, многоагентные системы